

DAMAGE RESISTANCE IN COMPOSITE MATERIALS

P.V. Straznicky¹, C. Poon², M.J. Worswick¹, E. Fuoss¹, O. Majeed¹, H. Vietinghoff³

1 - Carleton University, Ottawa, Canada K1S 5B6

2 - Structures, Materials and Propulsion Laboratory, IAR, Ottawa, Canada

3 - General Motors Corp., London, formerly Carleton University, Ottawa

ABSTRACT

Damage resistance in composite materials is an important property as it provides a means of evaluating and comparing different material systems, layups and structures on the basis of their propensity for damage. The Structures, Materials and Propulsion Laboratory of the Institute for Aerospace Research (SMPL-IAR) and Carleton University (CU) have been collaborating on a research project to understand impact damage resistance and to develop a method for its prediction.

Initially, a database was developed containing low-velocity impact test results on coupons made from two different material systems. Then, analytical and numerical modelling were undertaken with the aim to isolate parameters which control the impact damage resistance. Individual parameters such as the peak impact force were found unsuitable, and a combined parameter is being developed. Numerical simulations of impact, using LS-DYNA3D code, have resulted in reasonable predictions of matrix damage and fibre breakage.

INTRODUCTION

With the increasing use of composite materials, the need to predict damage resulting from a low velocity impact becomes important. The prediction capability would permit considerations of damage resistant material systems, layups and structural features during the design process. At present, if such considerations are used, they are based on extensive and costly tests. Improvements to this approach are limited by a lack of substantiated parameters which govern damage initiation and propagation. Significant efforts have been made to identify these key parameters and to use them to develop a standard method for impact damage resistance assessment but no such method has emerged so far. This is mainly due to the complexity of the phenomena involved.

The ultimate goal of the collaborative research between SMPL-IAR and CU is to develop a method to predict impact damage resistance that could be incorporated into an existing computer design system for composites. The research programme consists of impact testing followed by extensive characterization of the resulting damage, data analyses and development of the damage resistance parameters. In parallel, numerical modelling of impact including damage prediction has been undertaken to improve our understanding of impact damage initiation and propagation, and to provide analytical capabilities in this important area. The results to-date and main conclusions of the work are presented in this paper.

EXPERIMENTAL WORK

In the initial phase of the project, a large number of rectangular (102x152 mm) test specimens were made from Toray T800H/3900-2 and Hercules AS4/3501-6 material systems in six different layups. The specimens were impacted in a drop tower at impact velocities ranging from 1.4 to 4.8 m/s while keeping the drop mass constant, to achieve impact energies up to 60 J. Fabrication and impact tests met the Boeing Specification BSS 7260 [1]. Contact force and strain (at selected locations) histories were acquired. Damage was characterized using pulse-echo C-scan ultrasonic, X-ray and fractographic examinations. For details, see [2] which also deals with compression-after-impact tests. The experimental data was analyzed with respect to different parameters and a "damage resistance envelope" was plotted for the Toray material in quasi-isotropic layups, as shown in Fig.1.

Figure 1. Damage Resistance Envelope for T800H/3900-2 Material, (45/0/-45/90)_{ns} Layup, Simply-supported Rectangular Plate

This figure is an example of information that is useful for structural design and for damage tolerance evaluations to predict the characteristic damage states. Unfortunately, development of such envelopes from experiments would be costly for the large number of material combinations and layups suitable for structural applications.

ANALYTICAL STUDIES

Research to-date has approached the damage resistance from different directions and the results of recent work, [3] to [8], can be summarized as follows:

- The peak impact force is a key material characteristic of damage resistance in composites.
- The total fracture energy absorbed by the plate during the impact should correspond to the amount of damage done [3]. However, Doucet and Rao [7] concluded that the absorbed impact energy may not be a suitable damage resistance metric.
- The level of visible damage can be used to compare or to predict impact damage in structures from coupon tests. Noting that US Air Force and FAA damage tolerance requirements are based on damage visibility, this may be a good damage resistance parameter.
- Understanding of the 3-D damage state (type, size and distribution of damage through thickness) is necessary for true assessment of damage resistance.
- It is highly desirable to develop a standard test method for determination of damage

resistance. A method proposed by Lagace et al. [6] centred on contact force, using static indentation for the reasons of simplicity and easy standardization. Static indentation was found to create virtually the same damage mechanisms and produce similar load-displacement as impact tests. The concern is that, at the same value of maximum load, the extent of damage will differ. Kwon and Sankar [8] found that static tests could be used to predict damage at velocities up to 2 m/s.

To evaluate the validity of the above findings, experimental data was analyzed using the previously suggested damage resistance parameters of peak contact force, absorbed energy, and indentation depth, [9]. The contact force history is a function of the type of damage which occurs in the composite specimen (i.e. matrix cracking, delamination, fibre breakage, material penetration). For all the layups studied, an almost linear relationship was found between impact energy and peak contact force. However, as Figs. 1 and 2 show, the damage area is a distinct function of the peak contact force for a fixed material, layup and thickness.

Figure 2. Investigation of Peak Contact Force as an Impact Damage Resistance Parameter, for T800H/3900-2 Material, 24 Plies, considering Interface Angle

It is thus clear that the peak impact force may be used, for example, to grade the damage resistance in production batches of composite components with a fixed design. It is not usable to predict damage within an arbitrary composite specimen. The same conclusions were reached for the other two parameters, absorbed energy and indentation depth. Apparently, no single parameter can be used to predict the damage resistance. Research is currently focusing on the development of a combined damage resistance parameter which covers structural features, layup and material; however, the approach has been simplified as discussed below.

Structural Response of the impacted structure influences the amount and type of resulting damage. It is affected by specimen (structure) size, curvature, layup, and boundary conditions. In the current research using coupon specimens, the effect of structural response is not being considered. The results are thus applicable only at those locations in structures where effects of curvature and of stiffening components can be neglected, e.g. mid-bay between stiffeners.

Layup Parameters include interface angle, thickness and number of potential delamination interfaces. Interface angle is the angle between the fibre orientations of adjacent plies. Varying the interface angle for quasi-isotropic layups, as seen in Fig. 2, gave significant differences in the damage area for a fixed impact condition. A hypothesis explaining the effect of interface angle on the formation of impact induced-delaminations, has been proposed. Liu [10] suggested that the size and shape of a delamination within an interface depend on the mismatch of bending stiffness between the plies adjacent to the interface. Liu impacted several $[0_4/\theta_4]$ graphite/epoxy specimens

at various ply angles θ and was able to generally predict the size and shape of the delaminations. However, extending this hypothesis to predict damage in multi-ply laminates was found to be inadequate for several reasons, as reported in [11]. It is expected that the influence of the interface angle will stem from the interlaminar shear stress initiating matrix failures. Shear stress distributions estimated using finite element analysis of the specimen under transverse static loading for θ of 15, 30 and 45 deg were used to normalize damage areas, with promising results (Fig.3).

Figure 3. Damage Area Dependence on the Interface Angle, Data Normalized

Thickness of a composite laminate affects the global structural response (the impact duration and peak contact force) as well as the damage initiation and propagation. For specimens with low bending stiffness, damage will initiate at the back surface where the bending stresses are the greatest. For specimens with high bending stiffness, the high contact stresses will cause damage to initiate underneath the impact site. It can be argued that thickness belongs to structural rather than layup parameters and, as such, it will be addressed in the next phase of this research.

Number of potential delamination interfaces: It has been shown that interfaces with non-zero interface angles are favourable to initiation and growth of delaminations. Since delamination growth absorbs impact energy, increasing the number of potential delamination interfaces will result in a smaller topographical damage area. This effect is demonstrated in Fig. 4 which shows the damage area vs. peak contact force for the standard layup $[45/0/-45/90]_{3S}$ and the ply grouping layup $[45_3/0_3/-45_3/90_3]_S$. By normalizing the ply group damage area by the ratio of potential delamination interfaces, the resulting data sets are in good agreement. The agreement is further improved when the ply group data is shifted to match the damage initiation points.

Figure 4. Damage Area Dependence on the Number of Potential Delamination Interfaces

Material properties such as fibre strength or matrix fracture toughness, have significant influence on the initialization, propagation, and the final state of impact damage within a composite.

From the above discussion, the following parameters were considered in the development of the combined parameter for impact damage resistance:

- Material: matrix strength S and interlaminar fracture toughness G .
- Layup: ply interface angle α and number of potential delamination interfaces N .
- Globally, the peak contact force P also gives an indication of the damage resistance.

The form of the combined damage resistance parameter has been developed by assuming that the damage resistance of a particular baseline laminate has been characterized. In this case the baseline is a Toray T800H/3900-2 in a 24-ply quasi-isotropic layup [45/0/-45/90]_{3S}, ref. [2]. In the following, the properties of the baseline laminate are denoted by a subscript 0. From experimental data it may be postulated that the damage area A is approximately equal to

$$A = a(P - b) \quad (1)$$

where a - slope, b - intercept (damage initiation). For the baseline conditions, $A_0 = a_0(P_0 - b_0)$ is known. If impacts at the point $P = P_0$ are compared, then

$$A = \frac{a}{a_0} \left[A_0 + a_0 b_0 \left(1 - \frac{b}{b_0} \right) \right] \quad (2)$$

In the above equation, the ratio a/a_0 is proposed to be a function of the interface angle, number of potential delamination interfaces, and the material system properties:

$$\frac{a}{a_0} = F_\alpha \left(\frac{\alpha}{\alpha_0} \right) F_N \left(\frac{N}{N_0} \right) F_S \left(\frac{S}{S_0} \right) F_G \left(\frac{G}{G_0} \right) \quad (3)$$

The ratio b/b_0 is similarly approximated. Functions "F" can be obtained from analytical work and from tests in which only one of the major parameters is varied at a time. Some of this work has already been done as discussed above, e.g. the effects of interface angle and ply grouping. The results are encouraging and the concept of a combined parameter appears to be feasible. The method becomes invalid once significant back face fibre breakage and splitting occurs. The limitations and possible approaches to overcome them will require further study.

NUMERICAL MODELLING

Numerical simulations of impact can also yield damage resistance data, and were done in parallel with the experimental and analytical work. Details can be found in [12] and [13]. Impact was simulated using LS-DYNA3D explicit finite element code [14]. A composite material coupon with [45/0/-45/90]_{3S} layup was modelled using Belytschko-Tsay four-noded quadrilateral shell elements to reduce computation effort. These elements do not consider the through-thickness normal stress, and do not accurately model the transverse shear stresses. The resulting shortcomings are the inability to model delaminations and the errors in global response of the specimen. To obtain a reasonable simulation of global response, a spring was added in series with the impactor. Stiffness of this spring was determined by static indentation tests of the composite coupons.

Low energy (5.2 J), elastic impact simulations were used to refine the modelling methodology and to study the effects of the following parameters:

- several different models of the tup and the support base
- coupon discretization (216, 864 and 3600 elements), hourglass control and contact stiffness.

The final calculations utilized solid element tup and base models, a coupon with 3600 shell elements, a numerical spring representing the coupon indentation stiffness, and default values (provided in DYNA) of hourglass control and contact stiffness. The predicted peak impact force and the period were within 4% and 6% of experimental values, respectively. The upper surface strains were also accurately predicted except for locations near the impact centre. It was concluded that the elastic impact simulations were satisfactory and that the model could be used in the attempts to simulate damage formation at higher energy levels.

Simulations which include the damage formation are significantly more complex. As soon as a failure is predicted, the material properties in the failed element must be changed to reflect degradation of its load-carrying capability. LS-DYNA3D contains a number of special material models and, in this study, a composite damage model (No.22) was used. The model is based on Chang-Chang failure criteria [15] and on post-failure degradation assumptions originally defined by Humphreys [16]. The failure criteria include fibre tensile failure, matrix cracking and crushing. The post-failure degradation is a complete in-plane unloading; for example, following the fibre failure in an element, the strengths and moduli are all set to zero.

Impacts at energy level of 30.4 J were calculated using the model optimized from the low energy simulations. The contact force history is shown in Fig. 5a, at three levels of coupon discretization.

Figure 5. Impact Simulations at 30.4 J Energy on a Standard Specimen, (a) Default Post-Failure Rules, (b) Modified Post-Failure Rules

Simulations 1H and 2H (216 and 864 elements, respectively) did not give any global indications of failure although matrix cracking was seen in the analysis of results. In simulation 3H (3800 elements) the contact force peaks at approximately 1.9 ms and the subsequent sharp drop gives a clear indication of fibre failure. The peak value of contact force can be thought of as a fibre failure threshold. The run 3H was repeated with failure simulation disabled. The results, shown as 4H, are similar to 1H and 2H. From the simulations 1H to 4H it is apparent that the global response of the model is dependent on the size of element and that the solution does not converge. A parametric

study was done to investigate the effect of reducing the fibre tensile strength on the failure progression. It was found that reduced fibre strength resulted in a reduction of the fibre failure threshold, an effect similar to reducing the element size. At a significantly reduced fibre strength, the solution predicted a catastrophic break-up of the specimen.

One factor which appeared to contribute to the overpredictions of the fibre damage and lack of convergence of the solution was the extremely conservative post-failure rules. Therefore, modifications to the rules were made such that the post-failure fibre stress and fibre modulus could be independently set by using parameters

$$\alpha_s = \frac{(\sigma_{11})_{post-fail}}{X_T} = \frac{\text{post-failure fibre stress}}{\text{fibre tensile strength}} \quad (4)$$

$$\alpha_E = \frac{(E_1)_{post-fail}}{E_1} = \frac{\text{post-failure elastic modulus}}{\text{fibre elastic modulus}} \quad (5)$$

An example of the effects of these modifications may be seen in Fig. 5(b) for four different magnitudes of $\alpha_s = \alpha_E$, representing a range of 0% to 20% residual fibre strength and stiffness after failure. As the residual strength increases, less damage is occurring. The simulation 3H-05 (5% residual strength) was analyzed further, and plots of projected damage areas were prepared. Fig. 6 compares the predicted to the experimentally observed damage. The matrix damage area is overpredicted while the fibre damage is predicted well.

Figure 6. Damage Comparison

CONCLUSIONS

The results of this research have led to the conclusion that single parameters such as the peak contact force are insufficient to characterize the damage resistance of a laminate. The large number of material, layup and structural parameters make a simple method for estimating the damage resistance difficult to develop. The proposed "combined" damage resistance parameter offers potential in overcoming this limitation. It has been shown that the method, in conjunction with a limited amount of testing, will provide reasonably accurate estimates of impact damage resistance.

Numerical modelling has provided damage estimates in terms of fibre breakage and matrix cracking which agree reasonably well with experimental data. There are, however, many outstanding problems that need attention. They include the mesh dependency seen in failure-modelling simulations, improvements to the failure criteria and post-failure degradation rules, and inclusion of delamination failure in the simulation.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was performed under NRC Subproject JGM-01, Impact Damage Tolerance in Composite Materials, and a Contract No. 31946-3-0007/01-SR with Carleton University. The partial financial support from NSERC research grant is gratefully acknowledged.

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